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100 Years of Quantum Mechanics

Jürg Fröhlich, ETH Zürich, Institute for Theoretical Physics, juerg@phys.ethz.ch

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100 Years of Quantum Mechanics

Jürg Fröhlich, ETH Zürich, Institute for Theoretical Physics, juerg@phys.ethz.ch

“Heisenberg’s type of mechanics has given me new hope and joy in life. To be sure, it does not supply the solution to the riddle, but I believe it is again possible to march forward.” (WOLFGANG PAULI)

Abstract

The revolutionary discoveries in quantum theory of the year 1925 are recalled. Key ideas that went into Heisenberg’s seminal work on matrix mechanics of July 1925 are reviewed in some detail. Dirac’s important contributions to the birth of quantum mechanics are hinted at. It is argued that we should and are in fact able to “march forward” in our comprehension of quantum mechanics.

1 1925: An ‘annus mirabilis’

‘Annus Mirabilis’ is a poem by John Dryden published in 1667. It commemorates the year 1666, which, despite the poem’s name, was the tragic year of the Plague and the Great Fire of London. The term has also been used to refer to Isaac Newton’s discoveries in 1665–1666, and to Albert Einstein’s discoveries of 1905¹. Here I use it to refer to the fundamental progress in quantum theory made in 1925, which has inspired the United Nations General Assembly to declare 2025 an “**International Year of Quantum Science and Technology**.”

This contribution reviews some of the key ideas that led to Heisenberg’s fundamental discovery of matrix mechanics in July 1925 [1], subsequently interpreted and extended in celebrated work by Dirac [2]. Readers, who want to understand more deeply how quantum mechanics was created are advised to consult van der Waerden’s collection [3] of the most important papers written between 1917 and the beginning of 1926, which also contains a lucid introduction written by him. My presentation is influenced by the courses on quantum theory taught by my teachers, Klaus Hepp, Markus Fierz and Res Jost [4] and, later on, by myself and by Norbert Straumann’s book on quantum mechanics [5]. Remarks by Alain Connes in [6] have helped triggering my interest in the history of these developments.

I would argue that, with regard to the quantity and depth of revolutionary progress in understanding how Nature works on the atomic scale, there was no other year in the history of physics comparable to 1925. It is thus natural to begin this essay with a list of the epochal discoveries made during that year, as reflected in the following works.

- 1924/25: Einstein’s work on ideal quantum gases [7]; prediction of Bose-Einstein condensation in Bose gases; first prediction of a phase transition using quantum statistical mechanics.

¹ I refer to ‘Wikipedia’ for further details about the meaning and the use of the term ‘annus mirabilis’.

- January 1925: Pauli’s discovery [8] of the (Pauli) exclusion principle and of electron spin as a “classically not describable two-valuedness of the quantum-theoretical properties of the valence electron,” as well as of its g-factor, $g_e = 2$; (see also [5, 9])².
- January: Paper by H. A. Kramers and W. Heisenberg on the scattering of light by atoms [11] following a series of earlier papers on related matters by various authors.
- May: Kuhn’s paper on what is called the *Thomas-Reiche-Kuhn sum rule*; (see [12] for the original results). This sum rule was instrumental in replacing the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization condition by a fundamental new one, namely the canonical commutation relations.
- July: Heisenberg’s revolutionary work [1] marking the discovery of matrix mechanics.
- September: Paper by Born and Jordan [13] on the mathematical formalism underlying Heisenberg’s matrix mechanics and extensions thereof, which they call *Quantum Mechanics*³.
- October: Goudsmit and Uhlenbeck [14] interpret Pauli’s “two-valuedness” as *spin* (Eigendrehimpuls) of the electron and propose an explanation of $g_e = 2$, which, however, was not tenable.
- November: Dirac proposes a crystal-clear mathematical interpretation and completion of Heisenberg’s discovery [2].
- November: “Dreimännerarbeit” [15]. Independently of Dirac, and shortly after him, Born, Heisenberg and Jordan propose a mathematical formulation of the new quantum mechanics. They develop the quantum theory of angular momentum and sketch extensions of quantum mechanics to systems with infinitely many degrees of freedom.
- January 1926: Pauli’s derivation of the hydrogen spectrum from the postulates of matrix mechanics [16]. (Since Pauli must have done most of the calculations in this paper late in 1925, and since it provided a convincing confirmation of the correctness of matrix mechanics, I count this paper among the triumphs of 1925.)

As is well known, the year 1926 saw further quite spectacular discoveries in quantum mechanics related to Schrödinger’s wave mechanics – a great source of powerful mathematical methods leading to important progress in the analysis of concrete physical systems, and, alas, a source of much confusion lasting until the present – and the work of Dirac and Jordan on quantum electrodynamics and quan-

² Pauli’s exclusion principle is fundamental for the stability of (non-relativistic) matter, systems of atomic nuclei and electrons, first established by Dyson and Lenard in 1967/68; see [10] and references given there. This property is one of the pillars which condensed matter physics rests upon.

³ The name “quantum mechanics” first appeared in a paper by Max Born, entitled “Über Quantenmechanik”, *Zeitschrift für Physik* **26**, 379-395 (1924).

tum optics ⁴. For lack of space I will not comment on these developments in any detail. The *Dirac equation*, the prediction of the *positron* and, more generally, of *anti-matter*, and *Dirac's path integral* [21] cannot be reviewed either. But a few sketchy remarks about some of the important further progress in quantum theory will be made at the end of this essay.

If I were asked to rank the discoveries mentioned above my choice would be the following one:

1. Heisenberg's discovery of matrix mechanics of July 1925.
2. Dirac's paper of November 1925, interpreting and extending Heisenberg's discovery.

In the following I try to reproduce the main ideas underlying Heisenberg's paper.

2 The basis for Heisenberg's discovery of matrix mechanics

During the years 1923 - 1925, it became increasingly clear that a radical change in the analysis of the structure and the spectra of atoms was indispensable. In the two leading centers, Göttingen (*Born*) and Copenhagen (*Bohr*), discomfort grew about the persistent problems encountered in the description of many-body systems ⁵ (e.g., the Helium atom and the H₂ molecule) within the old *Bohr-Sommerfeld-Epstein* quantum theory.

The way out of this impasse was found by *Heisenberg* in July 1925 and published in a paper entitled "*Über quantentheoretische Umdeutung kinematischer und mechanischer Beziehungen.*" (Heisenberg was 23 years old when he wrote this paper.) I quote a sentence from the introduction:

"[Es scheint] geratener, jene Hoffnung auf eine Beobachtung der bisher unbeobachtbaren Grössen, wie Lage, Umlaufzeit des Elektrons [im Atom], ganz aufzugeben, gleichzeitig also einzuräumen, dass die teilweise Übereinstimmung der genannten Quantenregeln mit der Erfahrung mehr oder weniger zufällig sei, und zu versuchen, eine der klassischen Mechanik analoge quantentheoretische Mechanik auszubilden, in welcher nur Beziehungen zwischen beobachtbaren Grössen vorkommen."

What earlier results could Heisenberg build upon when he made his epochal discovery? Here are four essential ones.

- A. *Rydberg-Ritz combination principle* [17] (1889, 1908)
- B. "Quantization" of integrable Hamiltonian systems according to the quantization rules of *Bohr-Sommerfeld-Epstein-(Schwarzschild-)Einstein* [18] (1913 - 1917)
- C. Theoretical work on scattering of light by atoms and (its relation to) atomic spectra by *Bohr, Heisenberg, Kramers, Pauli, Slater, Wentzel* and others, prior to 1925 and in January 1925; see [3]
- D. *Thomas-Reiche-Kuhn sum rule* [12]

Inputs C and D will enter our discussion in the next section. It deserves to be mentioned that the basis for Heisenberg's

⁴ It appears that Born always felt that his contributions to discoveries like this one were underappreciated.

⁵ classically, *non-integrable* Hamiltonian systems.

discovery was *atomic spectroscopy*; Planck's formula, which had stimulated much of Einstein's work on quantum theory, and *de Broglie's* discovery of the wave nature of particles did apparently not play an important role in Heisenberg's thinking.

A. Rydberg-Ritz combination principle

• For every species of atoms, there is a series of energies, $\{E_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, the "*Termschema*" or "*Grotrian diagram*" (which depends on the external electromagnetic field: Zeeman- and Stark effect), where E_n is the energy of an atom in a stationary state, $|n\rangle$, for all n , such that the frequency, $\omega_{n,m}$, of light emitted during an atomic transition from state $|n\rangle$ to state $|m\rangle$, with $E_n > E_m$, is given by ⁶

$$\omega_{n,m} = \frac{1}{\hbar} (E_n - E_m), \quad (1)$$

where $\hbar = h/2\pi$, and h is Planck's constant.

• Certain pairs (n, m) correspond to frequencies $\omega_{n,m}$ that are *not* observed: "*Selection Rules*".

• If $\omega_{n,m}$ and $\omega_{m,k}$ are observed then

$$\omega_{n,k} = \omega_{n,m} + \omega_{m,k} \quad (2)$$

is observed, too.

Within classical mechanics and electrodynamics, the Rydberg-Ritz combination principle cannot be understood. However, if, in Eq. (1), $n \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e., E_n approaches a threshold energy), with $|n - m|$ bounded, the predictions of the Rydberg-Ritz principle are assumed to agree with classical radiation theory; this is Bohr's "*Correspondence Principle*".

B. Quantization of Integrable Hamiltonian Systems

Consider a classical Hamiltonian system, S , with phase space $\Gamma \stackrel{\text{e.g.}}{=} \mathbb{R}^{2f}, T^*M$ (the cotangent bundle of some configuration space M), S^2 , etc. Let $\{.,.\}$ denote the *Poisson bracket* on the space of smooth functions on Γ .

DEFINITION: Let $f = \dim \Gamma/2$; S is said to be *integrable*, if there are f smooth, "independent" functions, G_1, \dots, G_f , on Γ in *involution*, i.e., satisfying

$$\{G_i, G_j\} = 0, \quad \forall i, j,$$

which are *constants of motion*, i.e., $\{H, G_i\} = 0, \forall i$, where H is the Hamilton function of S .

THEOREM (Liouville, Jacobi, Arnol'd, Jost, [20]):

Let S be an integrable Hamiltonian system with phase space $\Gamma = \mathbb{R}^{2f}$ and with the property that the level surfaces of constant G_1, \dots, G_f are compact. Then Γ is foliated by f -dimensional tori,

$$\mathbb{T}^f = \mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G}), \quad \text{with } \mathbf{G} := (G_1, \dots, G_f) \in \mathbb{R}^f,$$

that are invariant under the Hamiltonian flow generated by H and under the flows generated by the functions G_1, \dots, G_f .

⁶ In accordance with Heisenberg's *time-energy uncertainty relation*, relation (1) between the frequency of light emitted in a transition from a stationary state $|n\rangle$ to a state $|m\rangle$ turns out to be only approximate; excited states, $|n\rangle$, other than ground-states and symmetry-protected states, are *unstable*, namely *resonances*, and the corresponding energies E_n are (fuzzy) *resonance energies*; see [19] for a mathematical treatment of these matters.

Every invariant torus $\mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G})$ can be parametrized by f angle variables, $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = (\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_f)$, where $\varphi_i \in [0, 2\pi]$ parameterizes the i^{th} non-contractable cycle of $\mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G})$, for $i = 1, \dots, f$. Since the functions G_i are constant on every torus $\mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G})$ and independent, in the sense that their gradients, dG_1, \dots, dG_f , are everywhere linearly independent, one can introduce functions, W_1, \dots, W_f , called *action variables*, which only depend on G_1, \dots, G_f , such that

$$\{W_i, W_j\} = 0, \{W_i, \varphi_j\} = \delta_{ij}, \text{ and } \{\varphi_i, \varphi_j\} = 0, \forall i, j.$$

The Hamilton function H of S is a function of the action variables alone. In general, the mechanical flow on $\mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G})$ is not periodic but *quasi-periodic* in time t , which represents a problem for the original Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization.

Generalization of the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rules

The “allowed orbits” (stationary states), $|n\rangle$, of S lie on tori $\mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{W}_n) \equiv \mathbb{T}^f(\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{W}_n))$, where \mathbf{W}_n satisfies

$$\mathbf{W}_n = (W_1, \dots, W_f) = h \mathbf{n}, \quad \mathbf{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_f) \in \mathbb{Z}^f. \quad (3)$$

The integers n_1, \dots, n_f are called *quantum numbers*. The corresponding “energy levels” of S are given by

$$E_n = H(\mathbf{W}_n). \quad (4)$$

This generalization of the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rules is due to *Einstein* (1917) [18], who also pointed out that, according to *Poincaré*, the three-body Coulomb problem is not integrable, which explains why already the Helium atom could not be understood using Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rules.

Let X be an “observable” of S , i.e., X is a real-valued smooth function on $\Gamma = \mathbb{R}^{2f}$. In the following we imagine that S contains particles interacting with the electromagnetic field, and that X is, for example, proportional to a component of the total electric dipole moment of S . For $\mathbf{W} = \text{const.}$, $X = X(\boldsymbol{\varphi}, \mathbf{W})$ is a periodic function of the angle variables $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = (\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_f)$. We expand it in a *Fourier series*,

$$X(\boldsymbol{\varphi}, \mathbf{W}) = \sum_{\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^f} \hat{X}_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{W}) e^{i\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}}.$$

The *time evolution* of X can be derived from the time evolution of the angle variables,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\varphi}_i &= \{H, \varphi_i\} = \frac{\partial H(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_i} =: \omega_i(\mathbf{W}), \\ \dot{W}_j &= \{H, W_j\} \equiv 0, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, f. \end{aligned}$$

The solutions of these Hamiltonian equations of motion are

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{const.}, \quad \boldsymbol{\varphi} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}_0 + \boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot t, \quad \text{with } \boldsymbol{\omega} = \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{W}).$$

Thus

$$X(t) = \sum_{\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^f} \hat{X}_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{W}) e^{i(\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}_0 + [\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{W})] \cdot t)},$$

We observe that $X(t)$ is a *quasi-periodic* function of time t , with frequencies $\boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n})} \equiv \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}$.

If S were a classical Hamiltonian system, and if X were a component of the total electric dipole moment of charges in S , then the Maxwell equations would imply that electromagnetic radiation with frequencies $\boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n})}$, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^f$, would

be emitted; (the recoil of the electromagnetic field on the motion of charges in S is neglected here)⁷. For every fixed \mathbf{W} , the frequencies $\boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n})} = \boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n})}(\mathbf{W})$ define a representation of the *abelian group* \mathbb{Z}^f ,

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n})} + \boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{m})} = \boldsymbol{\omega}^{(\mathbf{n}+\mathbf{m})}, \quad \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}^f.$$

Hence, with some frequency $\boldsymbol{\omega}$, all its harmonics, $n\boldsymbol{\omega}$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$, would in general be emitted, too! This is *not* observed in Nature and *contradicts* the Rydberg-Ritz principle.

Consider an atom, S . In Nature, frequencies of electromagnetic radiation emitted by electrons in S actually represent a *groupoid* (not a group), \mathcal{G} , consisting of pairs, (\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{n}) , of “quantum numbers” labeling “stationary states,” $|n\rangle$ and $|m\rangle$, of S ; see Eqs. (3) and (4). For (\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{k}) and (\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{n}) in \mathcal{G} , $(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{k}) \circ (\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{n}) = (\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{n})$ belongs to \mathcal{G} , too. (The composition, $(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{k}) \circ (\ell, \mathbf{n})$, of (\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{k}) with (ℓ, \mathbf{n}) is defined if and only if $\mathbf{k} = \ell$.)

The Rydberg-Ritz principle implies that the frequencies

$$\omega_{m,n} := \frac{1}{h}(E_m - E_n) \quad (5)$$

define a representation of \mathcal{G} .

3 Heisenberg’s breakthrough of July 1925

Let S be a hydrogen atom or a system of harmonic oscillators; S is thus an integrable system. Then $E_n = H(\mathbf{W} = h \mathbf{n})$, see Eq. (4), is the energy of an “allowed orbit” (stationary state), $|n\rangle$, of the quantization of S ; see (3). This yields the correct “*Termschema*” for the spectral lines of hydrogen and of systems of harmonic oscillators and the correct degeneracies of their stationary states. The problem Heisenberg attempts to solve is to develop a *new mechanics* that does not depend on S being integrable. He proposes that the new mechanics be formulated exclusively in terms of “*observable quantities*”. Given the “*Termschema*” $\{E_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ of some system S , he associates a *stationary state*, $|n\rangle$, with every energy E_n , for all n , and assumes that all the “*observables*,” such as the total electric dipole moment of charges in S , *only* depend on *pairs* (m, n) corresponding to observed transitions between stationary states $|m\rangle$ and $|n\rangle$ of S .

Thus, when quantizing a classical Hamiltonian system in accordance with the new mechanics, the Fourier coefficients, $\hat{X}_{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{W} = h \mathbf{m})$, of a function X on its phase space are to be replaced by what Heisenberg called (number-) “*schemes*”, \hat{X} , with

$$\hat{X} = (X_{m,n})_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{G}},$$

where \mathcal{G} is the groupoid of pairs of quantum numbers corresponding to observed transitions between stationary states of the quantized system. (Here $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^f$ is replaced by a general index $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$.)

Remark: If X is proportional to the electric dipole moment of S then the entry $X_{m,n}$ in the “scheme” $\hat{X} = (X_{m,n})_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{G}}$ corresponding to X after $_{m,n}$ quantizing S has the property that $|X_{m,n}|^2$ is proportional to the intensity of light with frequency $\omega_{m,n} = \frac{1}{h}(E_m - E_n)$ emitted in the transition from state $|m\rangle$ to state $|n\rangle$. This is suggested by earlier results on atomic

⁷ This fact was discovered, in theory and experiment, by *Heinrich Hertz*.

spectra alluded to in Input C, Sect. 3. Hence $X_{m,n}$ can be considered to be “*observable*”. Heisenberg’s schemes were subsequently recognized by *Born* and *Jordan* and by *Dirac* to be *matrices* [13, 2].

Returning to the special case of an integrable Hamiltonian system S , Bohr’s “*Correspondence Principle*” suggests that, after quantizing S ,

$$X_{m,m+n} \approx \hat{X}_n(\mathbf{W} = h\mathbf{m}), \text{ for } 0 < |\mathbf{n}| \ll |\mathbf{m}|. \quad (6)$$

Since, classically, X is a *real* function on the phase space of S one has that

$$\hat{X}_{-n}(\mathbf{W}) = \hat{X}_n(\mathbf{W})^*,$$

where $*$ is complex conjugation. With Eq. (6) this suggests that $X_{m,n}^* = X_{n,m}$, i.e., \hat{X} is a hermitian matrix.

If $X^{(1)}$ and $X^{(2)}$ are two classical “observables” of S then their product $X^{(1)} \cdot X^{(2)}$ is an “observable,” too; (smooth functions on phase space form an abelian algebra). Then

$$\overline{(X^{(1)} \cdot X^{(2)})_n(\mathbf{W})} = \sum_{\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}^f} \hat{X}_{n-\mathbf{m}}^{(1)}(\mathbf{W}) \cdot \hat{X}_{\mathbf{m}}^{(2)}(\mathbf{W}),$$

i.e. the Fourier coefficients of the product $X^{(1)} \cdot X^{(2)}$ are given by the convolution of the Fourier coefficients of $X^{(1)}$ and $X^{(2)}$. Heisenberg proposes to replace the *convolution product* on the group \mathbb{Z}^f by the product

$$(\hat{X}^{(1)} * \hat{X}^{(2)})_{m,n} = \sum_k X_{m,k}^{(1)} \cdot X_{k,n}^{(2)}, \quad (7)$$

which is the *matrix product* of $\hat{X}^{(1)}$ and $\hat{X}^{(2)}$. Setting $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{p}$, $\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{\ell}$, with $|\mathbf{p}| \ll |\mathbf{m}|$, $|\mathbf{\ell}| \ll |\mathbf{m}|$, the matrix product (7) is seen to approach the convolution product, in accordance with Bohr’s correspondence principle.

The next problem Heisenberg had to face concerns the *time evolution* of “observables” \hat{X} . Supposing that S is an integrable system with the property that

$$E_n = H(\mathbf{W} = h\mathbf{n})$$

is the energy of an “*allowed orbit*”, $|\mathbf{n}\rangle$, we find that

$$\hbar \omega_{m,n} \stackrel{(4)}{=} E_m - E_n \approx \nabla H(\mathbf{W} = h\mathbf{m}) \cdot h(\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n}), \quad (8)$$

for $|\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n}| \ll |\mathbf{m}|$.

Using the Rydberg-Ritz combination principle, with the frequency condition (8), and Bohr’s correspondence principle (6), one arrives at the idea that

$$X_{m,n}(t) = e^{i\omega_{m,n} t} X_{m,n} = e^{i(E_m t)/\hbar} X_{m,n} e^{-i(E_n t)/\hbar}. \quad (9)$$

Heisenberg generalizes (9) by replacing the Hamilton function H of a classical system S by a “*diagonal scheme*” (i.e., a diagonal matrix), $\hat{H} = (H_{m,n})$, the *Hamiltonian* of S , given by

$$H_{m,n} = E_m \delta_{m,n},$$

where the quantum number m corresponds to the stationary state $|m\rangle$ of energy E_m of the quantization of S , and he proposes that the time evolution of a general “observable” $\hat{X} = (X_{m,n})$ be given by

$$X_{m,n}(t) = [e^{i\hat{H}t/\hbar} * X * e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar}]_{m,n}. \quad (10)$$

This equation was baptized *Heisenberg equation* by Dirac. Following the philosophy of the young Einstein, namely to

formulate a theory entirely in terms of observable quantities⁸, Heisenberg now proposes to *ban* the Bohr-Sommerfeld rules for “*allowed (mechanical) orbits*” of integrable systems, as expressed in the conditions

$$\mathbf{W}_n = h\mathbf{n}, \quad \mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^f, \quad E_n = H(\mathbf{W}_n),$$

because classical orbits are not observable (and most systems S are not integrable). He finds an appropriate replacement of these rules in the *Thomas-Reiche-Kuhn sum rules*, input D, Sect. 2, which we discuss next.

Let x be a component of the position of an electron (mass M) in the shell of an atom. By $p = M\dot{x}$ we denote the corresponding component of its momentum. As explained above, Heisenberg replaces x by a matrix $\hat{X} = (X_{m,n})$ and p by a matrix $\hat{P} = (P_{m,n})$. He proposes to preserve the classical relation between the position and the momentum, setting $\hat{P} = M\dot{\hat{X}}$. Eq. (10) then implies that

$$P_{m,n} = M\dot{X}_{m,n} = iM\omega_{m,n} X_{m,n},$$

with $\omega_{m,n} = \frac{i}{\hbar}(E_m - E_n) = -\omega_{n,m}$.

Heisenberg considers the commutator

$$\begin{aligned} -i[\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{n,n} &\equiv -i \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}_+} (X_{n,m} \cdot P_{m,n} - P_{n,m} \cdot X_{m,n}) \\ &= 2M \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}_+} |X_{n,m}|^2 \omega_{m,n}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The quantity $|X_{m,n}|^2$ had appeared in calculations of the intensity of the spectral line corresponding to a transition from a state $|n\rangle$ to a state $|m\rangle$. The right side of Eq. (11) is the basic expression appearing in the *Thomas-Reiche-Kuhn sum rule*, which says that *this expression is equal to Planck’s constant \hbar* . It is straightforward to argue that, for a *harmonic oscillator*, this sum rule is correct.

The classical equation of motion of the harmonic oscillator is $M\ddot{x} = -fx$, where f is the spring constant. The frequency of the oscillator is given by $\omega = \sqrt{f/M}$. The solutions of these equations of motion are

$$x_i(\xi) = \xi \cos(\omega t + \theta), \quad \dot{x}_i(\xi) = -\omega \xi \sin(\omega t + \theta),$$

for constants $\xi \geq 0$ and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ determined by the initial conditions; (t denotes time). The energy of this solution is

$$E(\xi) = \frac{M}{2} \dot{x}_i(\xi)^2 + \frac{M\omega^2}{2} x_i(\xi)^2 = \frac{M\omega^2}{2} \xi^2$$

According to Planck, the energies of “*allowed orbits*” (*stationary states*) are given by $E(\xi_n) \equiv E_n = n\hbar\omega$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, (zero-point energy neglected). This follows from the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization condition

$$\int p \cdot dx = nh,$$

for an “*allowed orbit*.” Thus, for a given n ,

$$\xi \equiv \xi_n = \sqrt{\frac{2n\hbar}{M\omega}}.$$

Following Heisenberg’s ideas, one sets

$$X_{n,n+1} \simeq \hat{x}_1(\xi_n) = \frac{1}{2}\xi_n, \quad X_{n,n-1} \simeq \hat{x}_{-1}(\xi_{n-1}) = \frac{1}{2}\xi_{n-1},$$

⁸ which Einstein had already abandoned in 1925

$(X_{n,m} = 0, \text{ for } |n - m| > 1)$ and

$$\omega_{n+1,n} = (n + 1)\omega - n\omega = \omega = \omega_{n,n-1} = -\omega_{n-1,n}.$$

It then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} -i[\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{n,n} &= -i[\hat{X}, M\dot{\hat{X}}]_{n,n} = 2M\{|X_{n,n+1}|^2 \omega_{n+1,n} + |X_{n,n-1}|^2 \omega_{n-1,n}\} \\ &= 2M\omega \frac{1}{4} \{\xi_n^2 - \xi_{n-1}^2\} = \frac{M\omega}{2} \frac{2\hbar}{M\omega} \{n - (n - 1)\} \\ &= \hbar. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Next, one would like to determine the matrix elements $[\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{m,n}$ for $m \neq n$. This was first done by Born and Jordan in [13]⁹.

4 Completing matrix mechanics to quantum mechanics

Born and Jordan interpret Heisenberg's "schemes" as *matrices* and further develop the *mathematical formalism of matrix mechanics*. Following Heisenberg, they replace real-valued functions on classical phase space by *hermitian matrices*, they replace Hamilton functions of the form

$$H(p, x) = \frac{p^2}{2M} + V(x)$$

by *Hamilton operators* (Hamiltonians)

$$\hat{H} := \frac{\hat{P}^2}{2M} + V(\hat{X}), \quad (13)$$

and, following Heisenberg, they demand that the Heisenberg equations of motion for \hat{X} and \hat{P} have the same form as the classical Hamiltonian equations of motion. Thus,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{X} \equiv \dot{\hat{X}} = \frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}, \hat{X}] \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{\hat{P}}{M}, \quad \dot{\hat{P}} = \frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}, \hat{P}] \stackrel{!}{=} -\text{grad}V(\hat{X}),$$

for \hat{H} as in (13). It follows that

$$\frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}, [\hat{X}, \hat{P}]] = [\dot{\hat{X}}, \hat{P}] + [\hat{X}, \dot{\hat{P}}] = \left[\frac{\hat{P}}{M}, \hat{P}\right] - [\hat{X}, \text{grad}V(\hat{X})] = 0.$$

Next,

$$\frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}, [\hat{X}, \hat{P}]]_{m,n} = \frac{i}{\hbar} (E_m - E_n) [\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{m,n} = i\omega_{m,n} [\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{m,n}.$$

Assuming that $E_m \neq E_n$, for $m \neq n$, it follows that

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{P}]_{m,n} = 0, \text{ for } m \neq n \quad (14)$$

Together with Eq. (12) (Thomas-Reiche-Kuhn sum rule), it follows that

$$[\hat{X}, \hat{P}] = i\hbar \mathbf{1},$$

which are the *canonical commutation relations*. These relations replace the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization conditions. With the hermiticity condition and the Heisenberg equations of motion for "observables" they completely determine the *algebraic structure of the non-relativistic quantum mechanics of a system of particles*.

⁹ When Born asked Pauli whether he was willing to help him work out the mathematical formalism clarifying Heisenberg's discovery and, in particular, determine the off-diagonal elements of the commutator $[\hat{X}, \hat{P}]$ Pauli replied as follows: "Yes, I know you are fond of tedious and complicated formalism. You are only going to spoil Heisenberg's physical ideas by your futile mathematics..."

The discovery of quantum mechanics holds a *miracle*: only approximately valid empirical rules (rules A, B and C, Sect. 2) gave birth to a mathematically consistent, perfect physical theory.

5 Dirac's contributions to quantum mechanics in 1925

Stimulated by Heisenberg's discovery of July 1925, Dirac proposes the following general rules to pass from classical Hamiltonian mechanics to quantum mechanics [2]:

Let Γ be the phase space of a Hamiltonian system S with Poisson bracket $\{.,.\}$.

- Let F be an arbitrary real function on Γ . In order to quantize S , F must be replaced by a *hermitian matrix* \hat{F} . Specializing to ordinary mechanical systems of particles moving in physical space, then, up to ordering problems, this is accomplished by replacing $F(x, p)$ by $\hat{F} = F(\hat{X}, \hat{P})$, with \hat{X} and \hat{P} satisfying the canonical commutation relations.
- The product, $F \cdot G$, of two functions, F and G , on Γ must be replaced by the matrix product, $\hat{F} * \hat{G}$, of the quantizations of F and G .
- The Poisson bracket, $\{F, G\}$, of F and G must be replaced by commutator, $\frac{i}{\hbar} [\hat{F}, \hat{G}]$, of their quantizations.

Dirac notices that the algebraic structure of the family of quantum-mechanical observables is preserved under similarity transformations,

$$\hat{F} \mapsto T \cdot \hat{F} \cdot T^{-1}, \quad (15)$$

for an arbitrary invertible matrix T . In order to preserve the *hermiticity* of observables under the transformation in (15), one must require T to be *unitary*, i.e., $T^* = T^{-1}$.

6 Completing quantum mechanics

"It seems clear that the present quantum mechanics is not in its final form." (P. A. M. DIRAC)

Three further fundamental contributions should be mentioned:

1. *Von Neumann's uniqueness theorem*: The quantization of the phase space $\Gamma = \mathbb{R}^{2f}$, with the (exponentiated) canonical commutation relations, the so-called *Weyl relations*,

$$e^{i(\hat{X}, a)} \cdot e^{i(\hat{P}, b)} = e^{i\hbar(a \cdot b)} e^{i(\hat{P}, b)} \cdot e^{i(\hat{X}, a)},$$

imposed, is *unique*. This means that Schrödinger's configuration space representation of the basic observables of quantum mechanics (1926),

$$\hat{P} = \frac{\hbar}{i} \nabla_x, \quad \hat{X} = \text{multiplication by } x,$$

can be used without loss of generality.

2. *Dirac's discovery of the path integral* [21]. Integration over "paths" or "trajectories", $\{x(s)\}_{s=0}^{s=t}$, can be used to calculate the matrix elements of the propagator,

$$[e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar}]_{x,x'} = Z^{-1} \int_{x(0)=x}^{x(t)=x'} \prod_{s=0}^t \mathcal{D}x(s) \exp[-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_0^t ds \mathcal{L}(\dot{x}(s), x(s))],$$

of quantum systems obtained by quantizing Lagrangian mechanical systems. Here Z is a normalization factor, and \mathcal{L} is the Lagrangian.

In 1905, Einstein discovered the *photon* and outlined a theory of the *photoelectric effect*. In 1916, he proposed a theory of (spontaneous and induced) emission and absorption of photons by atoms (A - and B - coefficients). In this work, *probabilities* first entered quantum theory! It contained a new derivation of *Planck's law of black-body radiation*. However, it did not represent a coherent quantum theory of electrically charged matter interacting with electromagnetic radiation, yet. Shortly after Heisenberg's discovery of matrix mechanics and Dirac's 1925 paper,

3. Dirac and Jordan made the first successful steps in developing a quantum mechanics of electrically charged matter interacting with the *quantized electromagnetic field*.

This signals the beginnings of *quantum electrodynamics* (QED) and of *quantum optics*; (see [22] and references given there).

Concluding remarks

"The constant element in physics, since Newton, is not a configuration or a geometrical form, but a law of dynamics." (WERNER HEISENBERG)

It turns out that taking into account the effects of interactions between charged matter and the quantized electromagnetic field is absolutely critical in the quest of a *general quantum-mechanical law of dynamics* enabling one to determine the *stochastic time evolution of states of individual systems* and thus for the development of a logically coherent *theory of measurements* as physical processes that properly expresses the probabilistic predictions for individual measurement outcomes, i.e., for a solution of the so-called *measurement problem*. This problem has been the cause of a lot of confusion about the deeper meaning of quantum mechanics that have lasted from the birth of quantum mechanics until today. A tentative completion of quantum mechanics, including a general law of dynamics and a resolution of the measurement problem, has been proposed in what I have called *ETH-Approach to / ETH-completion* of quantum mechanics; see [23], and references given there.

The reader may expect to find comments on further important topics, such as *interpretations of quantum mechanics*, Schrödinger's discovery of *entanglement* [24] and its diverse consequences and applications in quantum information and condensed matter theory, *hidden variables* [25, 5] (*Kochen-Specker theorem* and *Bell's inequalities*), *developments in quantum information theory and quantum computing*, etc. These topics ought to be discussed in a future contribution.

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